

TECHNISCHE
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Data management plan (DMP)

Simulation of tunnel resistance of Austrian railway tunnels

TunSim

Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0	03/12/2024	First version of the DMP – created for the start of the project

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List of acronyms

DMP	data management plan
RDM	research data management
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Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, we followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#) as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make our data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata.
- We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- TU Wien Policy for Research Data Management: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Policy%20for%20Research%20Data%20Management.pdf>
- TU Wien Code of Conduct – Rules to Ensure Good Scientific Practice: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Code%20of%20Conduct%20%E2%80%93%20Rules%20to%20Ensure%20Good%20Scientific%20Practice.pdf>
- Directives and Regulations of the TU Wien Rectorate: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/directives-regulations/>
- TU Wien Data Protection: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/data-protection-at-tu-wien>

1. Data description

1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced

Produced datasets

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	Railway tunnel map of Austria	Images	PNG	10 MB	no
P2	OpenTrack simulation output	Structured text	ASCII text	100 MB	no

Reused datasets

dataset ID	title	PID (e.g. DOI) or source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	Railway infrastructure data of Austria	https://mama-obs.oebb.at/obs20/	Licensed for research and teaching for TU Wien according to an agreement between ÖBB and TUW	yes
R2	OpenStreetMap (extract of Austria)	https://planet.openstreetmap.org/	Open Data Commons Open Database License (ODbL) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation (OSMF)	no

1b Data generation and reuse

Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

The experiment will be conducted by using the microsimulation software OpenTrack 1.10.7. The Railway infrastructure data of Austria are obtained from ÖBB-Infrastruktur's M-AMA interface which TUW's Institute of Transportation is allowed to use for scientific purposes. The Railway infrastructure database consists of 14 xlsx files.

As a first step, all tunnels of the Austrian railway network longer than 2 km will be identified in the railway infrastructure data (xlsx file "Bauwerke"). The tunnels' names, lengths, types of lining, cross-sections, gradients and maximum speeds will be exported from different tables (xlsx files "Bauwerke", "Geschwindigkeitslinien", "Koordinaten" and "Laengsneigungen") and processed with MS Excel or R into the ASCII text format needed for importing data into OpenTrack. Input data for the train shape values will be taken from literature. After importing the data, the simulation will be run.

The output of the simulation will be ASCII text files with running times and other information for each train and section. The data will be imported to Excel or R and compared to the running times calculated with empirical formulas in a report.

Finally, a map based on OpenStreetMap with the investigated tunnels highlighted will be drawn using R.

2. Documentation and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation

The filenames for P1 will be manually named `TunSim-Map-YYMMDD-verXY` while YYMMDD denotes the creation date and XY the version number.

The filenames for P2 will follow OpenTrack's naming convention as defined in chapter 8.7.2 of the OpenTrack manual (D. Huerlimann, A. Nash, *OpenTrack Simulation of Railway Networks*, Zurich) where the part before the full stop denotes the train number and the part after the full stop denotes the type of evaluation (e.g. velocity and and time). The relevant details will be included in a README file. Version control is done manually by choosing different output folders for different versions of the produced data. The folders will be named `TunSim-OTOutput-YYMMDD-verXY`, while YYMMDD denotes the date of the simulation run and XY denotes the version number.

As there are no domain specific metadata standards applicable, we will provide a README file with an explanation of all values and terms used at project level. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description or keywords when publishing data in open access repositories. In such a case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

2b Data quality control

The following data quality checks will be done: data entry validation. A manual check of the input will be conducted by the PI. In the R1 dataset, a range and consistency check will be performed with the xlsx files. If necessary the owner of the data will be consulted to check for correctness.

3. Storage and backup during research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by the project leader in cooperation with the responsible representative of TU.it. The infrastructure of TU Wien will be used for this purpose.

P1 (Railway tunnel map of Austria), P2 (OpenTrack simulation output), R1 (Railway infrastructure data of Austria) and the necessary parts of R2 (OpenStreetMap extract of Austria) will be stored on Server Housing: With this service provided by TU.it, the server is housed in a dedicated TU.it server room with limited access and operated by our research unit. Automated backup is provided by TU.it as well.

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. As it is foreseen to process sensitive data in the project (R1), advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated accordingly.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	writing	reading only
P2	writing	writing	reading only
R1	writing	writing	no access
R2	writing	writing	no access

Only project members who are employees of the research unit conducting the research will have access to data.

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

In an event of a technical breakdown of the TU server, the data will be recovered from the backup made by TU.it on a regular basis.

4. Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and ownership

Legal restrictions on how data is processed and shared are specified in the data processing and confidentiality agreement. The restrictions relate to dataset R1 (Railway infrastructure data of Austria). The legal restrictions are based on the following: According to an agreement between ÖBB-Infrastruktur and TU Wien, Institute of Transportation from October 2023, data can only be used by TU Wien for research and teaching. The circulation and publication of data requires written consent

of ÖBB-Infrastruktur. Outputs of research must be made available to ÖBB-Infrastruktur on demand.

Owner of the dataset R1 is ÖBB-Infrastruktur. Access is controlled by GB NZ unit at ÖBB-Infrastruktur and by M. Lagler at TU Wien.

Owner of the datasets P1 and P2 will be TU Wien, Institute of Transportation.

4c Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise. If necessary the Responsible Research Practices department of TU Wien will be consulted.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open	None	2025-02-27	TU Wien Research Data	DOI will be added later	<u>CC-BY-4.0</u>
P2	Open	None	2025-02-27	TU Wien Research Data	DOI: 10.70124/bq6sy-tpp81	<u>CC-BY-4.0</u>

TU Wien Research Data is an institutional repository of TU Wien to enable storing, sharing and publishing of digital objects, in particular research data. It facilitates the funders' requirements for open access to research data and the FAIR principles by making research output findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. A DOI is assigned to each dataset published in TU Wien Research Data. This service is developed by the TU Wien Center for Research Data Management and hosted by TU.it. <https://researchdata.tuwien.at/>

Methods or software needed to access and use data: Potential users need software to read and edit ASCII text files (e.g. Notepad++, LibreOffice Calc, R) and an image viewing software to open and edit PNG files.

5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	Members of the scientific community, Officers of local/national governments
P2	TU Wien Research Data	25 years	

6. RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

The PI (M. Lagler) will direct the data management process overall, with the research assistants responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained.

6b Resources

There are costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR as outlined below.

Cost name	Cost type	Description	Unit	Value
Data management personnel costs	Personnel	The PI will care for data management and will work for approximately 5 hours on data management resulting in costs of 500 EUR.	EUR	500
Estimated total costs			EUR	500

As the research project is a third-party funded project, these costs will be paid by the funding body.